

Bu proje Avrupa Birliđi ve Türkiye Cumhuriyeti tarafından finanse edilmektedir
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Technical Assistance for Turkey in Horizon 2020 Phase-II
EuropeAid/139098/IH/SER/TR

National Advisory Group Meeting on Horizon Europe: Solar Energy Call topics (Hybrid Event)

Date	18 November 2022	Time:	10:00-17:00
Venue	Hybrid Event & Radisson Blu Şişli, İstanbul		

Agenda

09:30-10:00	Registration	All
10:00-10:15	Welcome Note / Speech	Çađrı Yıldırım, Head of EU Framework Programmes, TÜBİTAK
10:15-11:00	HE Overview and Priorities in 2023-24 work programs for the Solar Community	Odysseas Spyroglou, Team Leader - Turkey in Horizon EU Programme Prof Derek K. Baker / ODTU-GUNAM
11:00-11:15	Coffee Break	
11:15-12:00	Presentation of the CST Calls <ul style="list-style-type: none">HORIZON-CL5-2022-D3-03-01: Innovative components and/or sub-systems for CSP plants and/or concentrating solar thermal installationsHORIZON-CL5-2023-D3-01-04: Solar Systems for Industrial Process Heat and Power	Dr George Karagiannakis, CERTH, CPERI

12:00-13:00	PV Calls <ul style="list-style-type: none">HORIZON-CL5-2022-D3-03-05: Novel Thin Film (TF) technologies targeting high efficienciesHORIZON-CL5-2022-D3-03-09: Recycling end of life PV modulesHORIZON-CL5-2023-D3-01-02: PV integration in buildings and in infrastructureHORIZON-CL5-2023-D3-01-03: Floating PV SystemsHORIZON-CL5-2023-D3-02-11: Advanced concepts for crystalline Silicon technology	Prof Rařit Turan /ODTU-GUNAM
13:00-14:00	Lunch break	
14:00-15:00	SolarHub Excellence Hub and SolarTwins Projects Opportunities and Synergies for the Greek/Turkish Solar Energy Ecosystems	Prof Derek K. Baker / ODTU-GUNAM
15:00-16:00	Presentations of successful ongoing projects in Solar Energy	Dr Mahmut Sami B¼ker / SOLİMPEKS R&D Dr Mehmet Eren / Head of PMO, Kalyon PV (TBC)
16:00-17:00	Wrap-up of the day / Q&A	